

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME:** Traore**FIRST NAME:** Mamadou Boussanga**PROGRAM CODE:** PHGH**COURSE CODE:** ACA-401D**PERIOD NUMBER:** 6**INSTRUCTOR:** Dr. Gulma**Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied xUS UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author xdid did *not* use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author xdid did *not* use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: xx%

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

QUIZ ASSIGNMENT FOR COURSE ACA-401D

QUIZ

1. Plagiarism is

- when the writer uses a source of information without giving credit to the author of that source of information.¹**
- When the writer uses any quote, paraphrase, statistic/data.
- When the writer uses a method to indicate where a piece of information came from.
- When the writers mention the source of where the information, they are writing about.

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1* (Bangui: Euclid University, 2021), 34.

2. Research is

- The collection and analysis of data but also on how you report your reasoning so that your readers can test and judge it before making your claims part of their knowledge and understanding.²**
- The presenting of findings in response to a question or proposition that we choose to address.
- is the systematic collection, analysis, and dissemination of data for the planning, implementation, and evaluation of programs.
- is the process of cleaning, analyzing, interpreting, and visualizing data using various techniques and business intelligence tools.

3. Sources are conventionally categorized into

- primary, secondary, and tertiary.³**
- Primary, secondary.
- Primary, secondary, tertiary, and quarterly.
- Secondary and tertiary.

4. WHO Member States are grouped in how many regions

- Six regions.⁴**
- Four regions.

² Kate L. Turabian et al., *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Ninth Edition: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers* (University of Chicago Press, 2018), 19.

³ Ibid., 36.

⁴ World Health Organization, *WHO Style Guide*. Second Edition (WHO, 2013), 3.

- Two regions.
- Eight regions.

5. A dissertation is

- is a systematic investigation of a socially significant research question that makes a contribution to the literature and demonstrates the skill of doctoral students to conduct original research to the literature and demonstrates the skill of doctoral students to conduct original research.**⁵
- Is the process of exploring a potential research topic.
- Is the ability to write and defend his or her philosophy of science, research questions, and method.
- Is the process of acquiring the basic research skills necessary to function as a behavioral scientist.

6. The dissertation introduction section includes

- Statement of the Problem.**⁶
- Critical Analysis of the Literature.
- Statement of Purpose.
- Research Design.

7. A research Argument is

⁵ James P. Sampson, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*. Second Edition (Tallahassee: Florida State University, 2017), 1.

⁶ *Ibid.*, 28.

more like a conversation with a community of receptive but skeptical colleagues.⁷

Is an action or process of talking about something to reach a decision or to exchange ideas.

Is an action or process of reasoning systematically in support of an idea, action, or theory.

Is a conclusion or resolution reached after consideration.

8. The dissertation Method section includes

Research Design.⁸

Research Questions.

Summary of the Findings.

Statement of the Problem.

9. Good communication Successful dissertation research is

To communicate effectively and regularly with your major professor, especially when difficulties arise. Be especially clear about how and when communication will occur.⁹

The ability to express your views and thoughts most efficiently and coherently.

⁷ Turabian et al. *Manual for Writers of Research Theses, and Dissertations*, 57.

⁸ Sampson, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*, 29

⁹ Ibid., 20.

- The ability to have a conversation with another person in an engaging way that is focused, consistent, and offers value.
- The use of communication tools and techniques to facilitate community participation and engagement and foster transformative social change.

10. the dissertation methodology section details

The scientific assumptions that guide the selection of methods used to answer the research question.¹⁰

- A schema for understanding the research design, variables, measures, participants, and data analyses that are used in the dissertation research.
- The nature of specific differences or relationships among variables that will be tested in the dissertation research.
- The research design, allows the reader to judge the extent to which using the design would adequately answer the research questions.

¹⁰ Sampson, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*, 41.

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